

GGOS DAYS

2023

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20.09 - 22.09

Yebes Observatory

Alcalá de Henares, Spain

WORKSHOP HANDBOOK

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10 Wednesday 20th

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Wednesday, September 20th

- 09:00 Opening Session
- 10:30 Recent Activities within IAG and GGOS
- 11:30 Keynote Speaker Session
- 14:10 GGOS Affiliates
- 15:00 Technical Visit of Yebes Observatory

Thursday, September 21st

- 09:00 GGOS External Activities
- 10:30 Making Geodetic Data & Products FAIR
- 11:15 Bureau of Networks and Observations
- 14:15 Bureau of Products and Standards
- 16:00 Splinter Meeting: GGOS Implementation Plan
- 18:00 Visit of Alcalá de Henares

Friday, September 22nd

- 09:00 GGOS Focus Areas
- 11:20 Closing Session

ggos.org/event/ggos-days-2023/

The **GGOS DAYS 2023 Organising Committee** is pleased to invite you to Alcalá de Henares (Madrid, Spain) and the Yebes Observatory on 20-22 September 2023, where this next edition will take place, organised by the **National Geographic Institute of Spain (IGN)**.

The GGOS DAYS meeting provides an opportunity to report on recent geodetic activities and to present plans, developments and achievements for the coming year. The meeting will take place in Alcalá de Henares, where part of the services of the **National Astronomical Observatory of the IGN** are located.

Alcalá de Henares has a remarkable cultural, architectural and gastronomic offer that you can enjoy during the conference. Located just 30 kilometres from Madrid, it was declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO in 1998. Alcalá is also known for being the birthplace of Miguel de Cervantes, famous for his novel 'Don Quixote'. The University of Alcalá is the oldest and most prestigious university in Spain, founded by Cardinal Cisneros in 1499.

During the meeting we will enjoy different **technical** and **cultural activities** such as:

- Visit to the Yebes Observatory and informal dinner of "paella", a typical Spanish dish.
- A visit to the city centre and a formal dinner in a local restaurant.

We look forward to welcoming you to the GGOS Days in Alcalá de Henares, Madrid!

Local Organizing Committee

José Antonio López Fernández
Esther Azcue Infanzón
Leonor Cui Domingo Centeno
Cristina García Miró
Aarón González Arriol

Elena Martínez Sánchez
Felipe Paredes Montalván
Víctor Puente García
Beatriz Vaquero Jiménez

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TRANSPORT

■ Transport from Adolfo Suárez - Barajas Madrid Airport to Alcalá de Henares City Centre

Recommended Option. Direct bus

Line 824

Connects Terminal T1 and T2 of Madrid-Barajas Airport with Alcalá de Henares.

Stops at the airport:

- Terminal T1. Floor 0. Arrivals
- Terminal T1. Floor 1. Departures
- Terminal T2. Floor 0. Arrivals
- Terminal T2. Floor 2. Departures

In order to get from one terminal to another (T1, T2, T3, T4), passengers and visitors can use a free bus transport service between the airport terminals, 24 hours a day.

Schedule and contact. From 6:00 am to 11:25 pm. Phone: +34 915 804 540

Interurban bus lines from “Avenida de América. Madrid” to “Alcalá de Henares”

Line 223. Madrid (Avda. de América) – Alcalá de Henares.

Line 227. Madrid (Avda. de América) – Alcalá de Henares (Espartales-Universidad)

No stops in the city centre

Line 229. Madrid (Avda. de América) – Alcalá de Henares (Virgen del Val).

No stops in the city centre

Night service line N202. Madrid (Avda. de América) – Torrejón de Ardoz – Alcalá de Henares.

More information:

ALSA

Avda. de América, 9A. Interchange of Avda. de América 28002. Madrid.

+34 902 42 22 42

www.alsa.es

Suburban train: Madrid Cercanías Renfe

Line C2. Chamartín - Atocha - Alcalá de Henares – Guadalajara

Line C7. Príncipe Pío - Chamartín - Atocha - Alcalá de Henares

From Madrid to Alcalá you can also go by train. These are the full names of the lines. They do not contain the name of all of the stops, only the main ones. Beware, if you take the C2 line, Alcalá de Henares will not be the last stop. Alcalá de Henares has several Cercanías' stops. Remember to check with Google Maps which stops is better for you.

Taxi

Taxis are always available at the airport. If you need to book a taxi from Alcalá to the airport:

Radio Taxi Phone Numbers. +34 91 882 21 88; +34 91 882 21 79
CC. Los Pinos, shops 30-31. www.alcalaradiotaxi.com

Uber and Cabify are also available in Madrid area.

Transport from Alcalá de Henares City Centre to the Venue

Venue

Alcalá de Henares IGN office in the Campus of the University.
 C. Escultor Claudio, 6A, 28805 Alcalá de Henares, Madrid

Transport to the venue

As the venue is located far from the city centre, a bus will be provided every day from the city centre to the venue. The meeting point for the bus will be the monument Puerta de Madrid at 8:00h on Wednesday and 8:30h on Thursday and Friday. People from the LOC will be in the meeting point. In that area, several recommended hotels are located (see hotels section below).

ONLINE PARTICIPATION

Join the GGOS Days 2023 from your computer, tablet or smartphone with following link for all 3 days:

meet.goto.com/ggos/ggos-days-2023

You can also dial in using your phone with the access code **636-710-733**. Phone numbers:

United States: +1 (571) 317-3129

Austria: +43 1 2060 92967

Germany: +49 721 9881 4161

Italy: +39 0 230 57 81 42

Switzerland:+41 435 5015 61

PRESENTATION SLIDES

The presentation slides will be available at the Zenodo platform:

zenodo.org/communities/ggosdays2023/

ACCOMMODATION

Here you can find some recommended accommodations close to the meeting point. Walking distance times are given.

Hotels

Hotel Evenia Alcalá Boutique ***	2 min
PCM Forum Alcalá ****	4 min
Hotel El Bedel ***	11 min
Parador de Alcalá de Henares ****	12 min
Hotel Cisneros ***	16 min

Hostels

Hostal Miguel de Cervantes	7 min
Hostal Complutum	11 min

COFFEE BREAKS AND LUNCHES

Coffee breaks, lunches and Wednesday dinner will be provided by IGN. For the formal dinner on Thursday see Social Events section below.

TECHNICAL VISIT OF YEBES OBSERVATORY

Wednesday 20th. A bus will take the participants from the venue to the Yebes Observatory.

13.2m VGOS telescope

The Yebes Observatory, located in Yebes, is a remarkable **scientific facility dedicated to astronomical and geodetic research and observation**. The Yebes Observatory is equipped with a wide range of instruments. The observatory operates two VLBI radio telescopes: the **40-metre and the 13.2-metre** VGOS telescope. It also has an **SLR station**, several GNSS stations and a gravimetry pavilion. In addition to the instruments, the Yebes Observatory has several laboratories and workshops.

In particular, it has a laboratory for cryogenic microwave amplifiers and passive devices, a laboratory for cryogenic radio astronomy receptors, a laboratory for electronics and detection devices, an electrochemistry laboratory, a laboratory for measuring microwave feeds (anechoic chamber), and two workshops with precision machining tools, including lathes, 5-axis machines and CNC machines, as well as general machining and metrology instruments. There is also a molecular spectroscopy laboratory that uses radio astronomy receivers and legacy astronomical observation instruments: a 14m radio telescope, a double astrograph, and a solar telescope.

40m telescope

YLARA station

As a highlight, we will have the opportunity to **visit the YLARA** (Yebes Laser Ranging) station. The station is in the phase of commissioning and will start regular SLR operation by early 2024. Upon completion of the construction of YLARA, Yebes Observatory will become the **first fundamental geodetic station in Spain**, hosting 3 major space geodetic techniques and a local-tie network to interconnect them. YLARA will also be able to track space debris.

The visit to the observatory will include a **coffee break** and will end with an informal **dinner of Spanish paella**, one of the most famous dishes of the Spanish cuisine. The bus will come back from Yebes at 22:00, arriving to the meeting point in Alcalá de Henares about 22:45.

VISIT TO ALCALÁ DE HENARES. FORMAL DINNER

Thursday 21st. A bus will be provided from the venue to the meeting point. A guided tour of the city centre will start at 18:00 in San Diego Square (in front of the old University building).

Alcalá de Henares has a long and fascinating history. The city dates back to Roman times, when it was known as Complutum. It thrived as an important **Roman city** and later became an Episcopal seat during the Visigothic period. In the 8th century, it fell under Moorish rule but was recaptured by the Christians during the Reconquista. The city experienced a significant **period of cultural and intellectual growth** during the Renaissance when Cardinal Cisneros founded the University of Alcalá in 1499. This prestigious institution attracted scholars and thinkers, including the **famous writer Miguel de Cervantes**, who was born in Alcalá de Henares in 1547. Today, the city proudly preserves its rich heritage and is a **UNESCO World Heritage Site**, attracting visitors with its historical charm and literary significance.

The **formal dinner** will take place at the local restaurant "La Cúpula" (C/ Santiago, 18, 28801 Alcalá de Henares - Madrid) at 20:00. The restaurant was the church of a convent in the XVII century. A group menu has been booked which includes the food, drinks, dessert, and coffee. The price of the menu is €47,5. Dinner is not provided by the organisation, each person needs to pay for their own menu. For organizing purposes, the main course has to be selected in advance. The **payment must be done in the registration of the meeting** (20th of September) by **only cash**.

09:00 - 10:00

Opening session

Chair: Esther Azcue

09:00

GGOS DAYS Opening

Laura Sánchez

09:15

Welcome to the GGOS days 2023

José Antonio López Fernández

09:30

Geodesy in Portugal: Situation and Projects [remote]

Helena Ribeiro

09:45

Geodesy in Spain: Situation and Projects

Manuel Sánchez Piedra

10:00 - 10:30

COFFEE BREAK

10:30 - 11:30

Recent Activities within IAG and GGOS

Chair: Basara Miyahara

10:30

IAG report

Richard Gross

10:50

The new GGOS Governing Board

Laura Sánchez

11:05

The new GGOS Strategic Plan

Laura Sánchez

11:20

GGOS Science Panel [remote]

Kosuke Heki

11:30 - 13:00

Keynote Speaker Session (Invited Presentations)

Chair: Laura Sánchez

11:30

Superconducting gravimeter

Its contribution to the observation of the Earth system

Ezequiel Antokoletz

12:00

Hydrodynamic levelling oriented to hydrodynamic models in coastal areas

Cornelis Slobbe

12:30

Glacial isostatic adjustment and its role in geodesy

Rebekka Steffen

13:00 - 14:10

LUNCH BREAK

14:10 - 14:55

GGOS Affiliates

Chair: Martin Sehnal

14:10

GGOS Japan

Basara Miyahara

14:25

GGOS D-A-CH [remote]

Hansjörg Kutterer

14:40

Towards a new GGOS Affiliate: Iberatlantic

Esther Azcue

15:00 - 22:00

TECHNICAL VISIT TO YEBES OBSERVATORY. PAELLA DINNER

09:00 - 10:00

GGOS External Activities

Chair: Laura Sánchez

09:00

GGOS Outreach Activities – Merging Efforts with IAG

Martin Sehnal

09:20

GGOS External Relations

Allison Craddock

09:40

Opportunities for interaction between GGOS and South America

Claudia Tocho

10:00 - 10:30

COFFEE BREAK

10:30 - 11:15

Making geodetic data & products FAIR

Chair: Detlef Angermann

10:30

Committee on DOI's for Geodetic Data Sets

Kirsten Elger

10:45

GGOS Portal – General Idea and Community Survey Results

Martin Sehnal

11:00

GGOS Portal – Feasibility Study and Perspectives

Lena Steiner, Martin Sehnal

11:15 - 12:50

GGOS BNO - Bureau of Networks and Observations

Chair: Mike Pearlman

11:15

Bureau Activity Report

Mike Pearlman

Reports of BNO Committees

11:25

SC on PLATO Report

Daniela Thaller

SC on Satellite Missions (SCM) Report [remote]

Roland Pail

SC on Data and Information Systems [remote]

Ryan Ruddick, Elisabetta D'Anastasio

IERS WG on Site Survey and Colocation [remote]

Ryan Hippenstiel

11:50

Reports of the IAG Services

IGS [remote]

Ryan Ruddick

IVS [remote]

Dirk Behrend

ILRS

Mike Pearlman

IDS [remote]

Jerome Saunier

IGFS [remote]

Riccardo Barzaghi

PSMSL [remote]

Andrew Matthews

12:50 - 13:00	GROUP PHOTO
13:00 - 14:15	LUNCH BREAK
14:15 - 15:30	GGOS BPS - Bureau of Products and Standards Chair: Detlef Angermann
14:15	BPS Activity Report Detlef Angermann
14:35	Some thoughts on the definition of EGVs [remote] Thomas Gruber
14:50	WG "Towards a consistent set of parameters for the definition of a new GRS" [remote] Urs Marti
15:00	Committee "Contributions to Earth System Modelling" [remote] Maik Thomas
15:10	Discussion
15:30 - 16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00 - 17:00	Splinter Meeting: GGOS Implementation Plan Invitation only
18:00	VISIT TO ALCALÁ DE HENARES
20:00	FORMAL DINNER

09:00 - 10:00

GGOS Focus Areas – Part 1

Chair: José Antonio López Fernández

09:00

Completion of the GGOS Focus Area on “Unified Height Systems”

Laura Sánchez

09:10

Focus Area Geohazard – Tsunami topic transition [remote]

John LaBrecque, Allison Craddock

GGOS Focus Area on Geodetic Space Weather Research (GSWR)

Michael Schmidt

09:15

Status and perspectives [remote]

Michael Schmidt, Ehsan Forootan

09:45

Recent Advances and Prospects of the JSGI:

Coupling Processes between Magnetosphere, Thermosphere and Ionosphere

Andrés Calabia

10:00 - 10:30

COFFEE BREAK

10:30 - 11:20

GGOS Focus Areas – Part 2

Chair: Laura Sánchez

10:30

GGOS Focus Area on Geodetic Space Weather Research (GSWR)

Benedikt Soja

FA AI4G: Study Group on “AI for GNSS Remote Sensing”

Milad Asgarimehr, Benedikt Soja

FA AI4G: Study Group on “AI for Gravity Field and Mass Change” [remote]

Alexander Sun

FA AI4G: Study Group on “AI for Earth Orientation Parameter Prediction” [remote]

Sadegh Modiri

11:00

Proposal for a new GGOS Focus Area on “Combined Tropospheric Products”

Harald Schuh, Rosa Pacione, Kyriakos Balidakis

11:15

Proposal for GGOS Focus Area on “InSAR GNSS”

Basara Miyahara

11:20 - 12:15

Closing Session: General Topics & Discussions

Chair: Laura Sánchez

11:20

The Growing Potential for K-Band (24 GHz) in Geodesy

Aletha de Witt

11:40

GGOS Days 2024

Laura Sánchez

11:50

General discussions

12:10

Closing of the GGOS Days 2023

Laura Sánchez

Members of the GGOS Consortium, GGOS Coordinating Board, GGOS Bureaus, GGOS Focus Areas, GGOS Science Panel, invited guests and all interested persons are cordially invited to attend this meeting.

IN PERSON PARTICIPATION

Country of Work	Full name
Argentina	Claudia Noemi Tocho
Austria	Lena Steiner
	Martin Sehnal
China, People's Republic of	Haixia Lyu
Germany	Ayomide Olabode
	Daniela Thaller
	Detlef Angermann
	Ezequiel Darío Antokoletz
	Harald Schuh
	Hermann Drewes
	Kirsten Elger
	Laura Sánchez
	Milad Asgarimehr
	Sadegh Modiri
Japan	Basara Miyahara
	Toshimichi Otsubo
	Yusuke Yokota
Korea, Republic of	Taehyun Jung
Morocco	Naima Bouhsane
Netherlands	Cornelis Slobbe
	Peter Teunissen
Portugal	Luísa Magalhães
Saudi Arabia	Rossen Grebenitcharsky
Sierra Leone	Agnes Sylvia Kallon
South Africa	Aletha de Witt
	Marisa Nickola
Spain	Andrés Calabria
	Elena Martínez Sánchez
	Esther Azcue
	Isabel Vigo
	José Antonio López Fernandez
	José Manuel Ferrándiz
	Luis del Peral
	Manuel Angel Sánchez Piedra
	Marcelino Valdés
	María Dolores Rodríguez Frías
	Maria Karbon
	Santiago Belda
Sweden	Rebekka Steffen
Switzerland	Benedikt Soja
United States of America	Allison Craddock
	Christopher DiLullo
	David Gordon
	Mike Pearlman
	Remington Oliver Sexton
	Richard Gross

ONLINE PARTICIPATION

Country of Work	Full name
Argentina	Federico Ibarra Flavia Leiva Florencia Romina Calizaya Florencia Toledo Mauricio A Gende Agustín Reynaldo Gómez Manuel Zeballos
Australia	Anna Riddell Diego Pinon Ryan Ruddick Luis Elneser
Austria	Gregor Moeller
Belgium	Carine Bruyninx Eric Pottiaux Fikri Bamahry
Benin	Segbedji Kossi Justin
Bolivia	Hernan Guerra Trigo Daniel Flores Vargas
Brazil	Gabriel do Nascimento Guimaraes Julia Isabel Pontes Roberto Teixeira Luz Salomão Soares Samuel Tarso da Silva Sonia Costa Tayná Aparecida Ferreira Gouveia Andrea Galudht Santacruz Jaramillo Luiz Filipe Campos Do Canto
Bulgaria	Lyubka Pashova Stanislava Valcheva
Canada	Sandra Bolanos Michael Craymer
Chile	Catalina Cáceres Estibaliz Echevarría Jesarella Inzunza Hermes García Ignacio Andres Parada Pichuante Juan Manuel Quilaleo Quintrel Nelly Sergio Rozas Bornes
China, People's Republic of	Cheng Wang Kaifa Kuang Kosuke Heki Xinggang Zhang Zeeshan Afzal
Colombia	Nancy Paola Gutiérrez Rueda Anllela Marsela Castillo Rey Daniela Hernández Edilberto Suárez-Torres Gabriel Andrés Ávila macheta Maida Mojica

Country of Work	Full name
Colombia	William Martínez-Díaz Nancy Paola Gutiérrez Rueda
Costa Rica	Mauricio Varela Sánchez Sara Bastos Gutierrez Carlos Eduardo Gómez Salazar
Denmark	Barbara Jenny Ehsan Forootan
Dominican Republic	Nolan Ricky Duran Quintana
Ecuador	Monica Zabala
Egypt	Abdelrahim Ruby
Ethiopia	Melese Wondatir Sisay Zenebe Ayele
Finland	Fabricio Prol Hannu Ruotsalainen Jaakko Mäkinen
France	Julio Alejandro Arias Gallegos Junchen Xue Laurent Soudarin
Germany	Alexander Kehm Aum Niranjana Mishra Daixin Zhao E. Sinem Ince Eri Stern Felix Müller Hanbing Peng Hansjörg Kutterer Jan Dostal Johannes Bouman Jürgen Müller Kyriakos Balidakis Marvin Reich Mohammad Mohseni Aref Mohammad Omidalizarandi Peter Steigenberger Tianqi Xiao Anastasiia Walenta Christina Dimopoulou Claudia Flohrer Lisa Klemm Mario Moreno Markus Goltz Michael Schmidt Sabine Bachmann Sarah Kowal Sonja Geist Thomas Gruber
Greece	Dimitros Anastasious Rafailia-Maria Mavromatidou Christopher Kotsakis
Honduras	Denis Alexander Aguilar Martinez
India	Arnab Laha Ratnesh Kushwaha

Country of Work	Full name
India	Ravi Kumar Muppidi Shilpi Chakraborty Shivangi Singh Vikash Kumar Abhishek Mhamane Ibaad Anwar Varuna Kumar Guddanti
Iran	Amirhossein Gholamzadeh Mahdi Farmahini Farahani Shahrokh Pourbeyranvand
Italy	Rosa Pacione
Japan	Yuto Nakamura Kensuke Kokado
Korea, Republic of	Young Jin Lee Mansoo Choi
Latvia	Jānis Kaminskis Lubova Sulakova
Luxembourg	Renaldo Sauveur
Morocco	Ahmed Imloul
Nepal	Loknath Sharma Pradeep Sapkota Upadhyaya Purna Jyoti Shakya Dipesh Suwal Kiran Bhusal Sandesh Upadhyaya
Netherlands	Dimitrios Psychas Lotfi Massarweh
New Zealand	Elisabetta D'Anastasio
Nigeria	Chukwuma Anoruo Dodo Joseph
Pakistan	Muhammad Choudhary Munawar Shah
Peru	Jaime Palomino Ruiz Katherine Doris Rodriguez Rocca Leonardo Alejandro Brañez Campos Franklin Maylle Vladimir Basilio Sulca Ñahui
Poland	Radosław Zajdel Dariusz Strugarek Dorota Marjanska Justyna Śliwińska Krzysztof Sosnica
Portugal	João Salmim Ferreira Manuela Vasconcelos Ana Carla Leal Coimbra Fernandes Bernardes Helena Ribeiro
Saudi Arabia	Sultan Falah Alshahrani
South Africa	Glenda Coetzer Roelf Botha
Spain	Assumpció Termens Joel Grau José Manuel Serna Puente

Country of Work	Full name
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Sri Lanka	H. W. Udaya Indika
Switzerland	Iván Herrera Pinzón Urs Marti
Tanzania	Thomas Daud Gisiri
Trinidad and Tobago	Arnessa Gooding
Turkey	Aydın Üstün Emel Zeray Öztürk Mehmet Arkalı Muge Albayrak
Uganda	Bruno Kyamulesire John Bosco Ogwang
United Kingdom	Andy Matthews Jonathan Jones
United States of America	John LaBrecque Lei Liu Alexander Sun Hermógenes Suárez Izabela Kevin Ahlgren Larry Hothem Maria Davis Sharyl Byram
Uruguay	Walter Humberto Subiza Pina Gustavo Fabián Caubarrère Diab
Venezuela	Andrea Marina Urdaneta Rivero Angel Jose Monroy Moreno Andry Zavala Arienay Jesmar Sánchez Pérez Douglas Bravo Jorge Luis Uzcategui Gil Juan Sheuat María Sánchez Nazarela Rojas Méndez Victoria Guerrero

NOTES

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